

Industry Perspectives on the Use of Large-eddy Simulation in Wind Energy

Established engineering models are being challenged by the trends of bigger turbines, larger wind farms, and complex terrain, to name a few.

While high-fidelity models like Large-eddy Simulation (LES) have the potential to address these issues, applications in the industrial practice remain rare. The main reason for this is the large computational demand.

Over the past years, the Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM) has been established as an alternative to classical LES approaches. With the help of graphics processing units (*GPUs*) the LBM can reduce the computational demand of LES by *more than two orders of magnitude*. This makes industrial applications of LES feasible, as demonstrated, e.g., by the automotive industry.

The availability of significantly faster LES raises the question: **How fast is fast enough?** Or, in other words, what are the industrial requirements to adopt LES for wind farms as a modelling tool. Please note, that we are referring to high-resolution LES (resolutions of 20m and below) including actuator line wind turbine models as illustrated below.

With the help of this survey we aim to answer *if* and *when* LES will be adoptable in the industrial practice. Furthermore, it will highlight what developments are still necessary and allow for a better targeting of fundamental academic research.

This survey is conducted by the Wind Energy Section at Uppsala University. The survey is fully anonymous and takes about 5 min. Results will be presented at the [Wake Conference 2023](#) and published open-access in the Journal of Physics Conference Series.

Thank you for your time and cooperation!

For questions and feedback please don't hesitate to contact Henrik Asmuth (henrik.asmuth@geo.uu.se).

* Required

Rendering of a LES of two turbines. Turbines modelled by actuator line models.

Section 1 of 4 - Your Background

1. My company is mostly active as a *

Mark only one oval.

- Wind farm developer
- Wind farm operator
- OEM
- Consultant
- Certifier
- No comment.
- Other: _____

2. How many years of experience do you have in the field of wind energy? *

Mark only one oval.

- < 2
- 2 - 5
- 5 - 10
- > 10
- No comment.

3. What is your personal experience with computational fluids dynamics (CFD)? This refers to RANS and/or LES.

I have ...

Mark only one oval.

- ... little to no understanding of CFD.
- ... a basic understanding of CFD (e.g., Bachelor or Master's courses)
- ... advanced knowledge of CFD (e.g., several years actively using CFD)
- ... expert knowledge of CFD (e.g., actively developing CFD software, PhD in CFD)
- No comment.

Section 2 of 4: Current Modelling Practices

4. Which of the following models does your company use **on a regular basis**? *

This can include AEP and/or load predictions.

Several answers possible!

Check all that apply.

- Engineering wake models
- BEM
- Dynamic wake meandering (DWM) models
- Vortex models
- Linearised CFD (e.g. Fuga)
- RANS
- WRF
- WRF-LES
- LES

5. The main factors limiting a wider use of CFD in my company are ... *

Several answers possible!

Check all that apply.

- ... the large run times.
- ... the large computational cost.
- ... a lack of expertise.
- ... the integration into existing workflows.
- ... bankability issues of model results.
- ... unclear benefits of higher fidelity models.
- I don't know.
- Other: _____

Section 3 of 4: Industry perspectives on the use of Large-eddy Simulation

6. Which of the following would be necessary for you to consider the use of LES? *

Rank on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 refers to *not important at all/the status quo is sufficient*, and 5 refers to *absolutely necessary/requires major improvements*.

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5	No Opinion
Faster run times	<input type="radio"/>					
Lower computational costs	<input type="radio"/>					
More validation of existing models	<input type="radio"/>					
User-friendliness of open-source models	<input type="radio"/>					
Availability of commercial models	<input type="radio"/>					

7. The following effects and flow cases can be challenging for many models used in the industry today. This can refer to both AEP or load predictions. LES holds the potential to address these modelling challenges. *

Where do you see the largest benefits in using LES?

Rank on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 refers to *not relevant at all/lower-fidelity models are sufficient*, and 5 refers to *very high relevance/lower-fidelity models are inadequate*.

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5	No Opinion
Complex terrain	<input type="radio"/>					
Stratification	<input type="radio"/>					
Blockage and gravity waves	<input type="radio"/>					
Wind farm wakes	<input type="radio"/>					

Section 4 of 4: A potential use-case for Large-eddy simulation

In the following questions we would like you to specify a *typical* case for wind farm modelling in your daily business, where you expect *benefits from using high-fidelity models*.

8. Specify the conditions of a the case. *

Mark only one oval.

- onshore, mostly flat
- onshore, complex topography and/or forest
- offshore

9. Specify the amount of turbines of this case. *

Mark only one oval.

- < 10
- 10 - 50
- 50 - 100
- > 100 (can comprise several wind farms)

10. What run time would be acceptable for this case? *

Note, that this refers to a single simulation, meaning one mean wind direction and one mean wind speed.

Mark only one oval.

- < 1 min
- 1 - 10 min
- 10 - 60 min
- 1h - 6h
- 6h - 12h

Thank you for answering this survey!

11. Do you have any further comments or feedback? (optional)

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